

Studies on Complex Compounds of Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) with 2'-Hydroxy-2,5'-Dichloro-4'-Methyl Benzal Acetophenone Oxime

M. C. BHARADWAJ and H. SINGH

Chemistry Department, D. S. College, Aligarh-202 001

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2'-Hydroxy-2,5'-dichloro-4'-methyl benzal acetophenone oxime (HDCMBAOX) was synthesised and its molecular formula was worked out on the basis of elemental and molecular weight analysis. The structural formula of HDCMBAOX was worked out on the basis of mass spectrometry. HDCMBAOX forms green, buff and yellow coloured metal complexes with Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) ions, respectively. The stoichiometry of the complexes was determined by conductivity, thermolysis and spectrophotometry.

Experimental

The mass spectra of HDCMBAOX were recorded on JMS-D-300 (JEOL Ltd., Tokyo) N.B. at EI mode at C.D.R.I., Lucknow at 70 eV and 100 μ A. Conductivity measurements were made with a Toshniwal conductivity bridge using dip type conductivity cell (cell constant, $K=0.73$). A Stanton thermobalance, model HT-SM, range ambient-1600°, with an accuracy of 1mg was used for TGA at a heating rate of 5° per min. Spectrophotometric properties of Ni(II) complex with HDCMBAOX were studied with the help of a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrometer.

Chemicals : 2'-Hydroxy-2,5'-dichloro-4'-methyl benzal acetophenone used was a purified sample. Hydroxylamine hydrochloride, anhydrous sodium acetate and other chemicals used were of AR grade. Standard solutions of nickel sulphate, palladium chloride and copper sulphate were prepared from B.D.H. reagents.

The oxime of 2'-hydroxy-2,5'-dichloro-4'-methyl benzal acetophenone was prepared by the reported method¹. It was recrystallized in carbon tetrachloride to procure colourless shining crystals of HDCMBAOX (m.p. 155°), yield 70.5%, elemental analysis C, 59.80 ; H, 4.00 ; N, 4.40 ; Cl, 22.20%.

Preparation of Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) complexes with HDCMBAOX : The metal complexes of Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) with HDCMBAOX were prepared by mixing 5 ml of $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ Ni(II), Cu(II) or Pd(II) solution with 10.5 ml of $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ HDCMBAOX solution in ethanol. Ammonia solution was added to obtain the pH of 9.2, 8.6 and 2.1 in case of Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II), respectively. Nickel complex (green), copper complex (buff) and palladium complex (yellow) so formed were filtered, washed with ethanolic water till the filtrate was free from the violet colour with $FeCl_3$ and then the complexes were dried.

For spectrophotometric studies, different sets of complexes were prepared and the complexes were extracted in carbon tetrachloride.

Gravimetric analysis of the Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) complexes with HDCMBAOX showed 8.380% Ni(II), 8.993% Cu(II) and 14.019% Pd(II) in the respective complexes. These results indicated the stoichiometry of the complexes as 1 : 2 (M : L).

The mass spectrum² analysis confirmed the molecular weight of HDCMBAOX as 321 as determined by other methods. The mass spectrograph showed the following major peaks at 323, 322, 321, 303, 180, 153, 149, 141, 137, 126, 124, 111, 106 and 76 m/e.

The peak at m/e 321 confirms the molecular weight of the oxime molecule. The peak at m/e 322 shows the presence of abundance of certain elements like hydrogen, oxygen, carbon and nitrogen in the compound. The peak at m/e 303 is due to the presence of -OH (phenolic) group in the molecule. Odd molecular weight also confirms³ the presence of one nitrogen atom per molecule according to the nitrogen rule. The peak at m/e 323 is due to the isotopic abundance of chlorine in the molecule⁴. The value of $R^s=11$ also shows the presence of two benzene rings and two double bonds in the molecule. The peaks at m/e 180 and 141 show the presence of double bond at position-2. The peak at m/e 106 shows the presence of chlorine atom at position-5', the peak at m/e 126 the presence of methyl group at position-4' while the peak at m/e 111 shows the presence of chlorine atom at position-2. On the basis of the above facts the following structure can be assigned to HDCMBAOX.

For establishing the stoichiometry of the complex species formed during the interaction of metal ion and HDCMBAOX, a series of conductometric titrations were carried out using equimolar concentration of reactants by direct method. The equivalence points in the titration curves corresponded to the formation of 1 : 2 complex for Ni(II) and Cu(II).

The thermal decomposition of Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) complexes with HDCMBAOX was studied as a function of temperature. It is clear that the complexes of Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) with HDCMBAOX were anhydrous in nature and there was no loss in weight upto 100°. Rapid decomposition took place at 200, 160 and 180° in the Ni(II), Pd(II) and Cu(II) complexes, respectively, the respective weight loss being 30.37, 30.61 and 25.60%. Formation of oxide took place at 760° and 800° in case of Ni(II) and Cu(II), respectively. In case of Pd(II)-HDCMBAOX, metallic palladium was observed at 780°. The Cu(II)-HDCMBAOX is thermally stable upto 180°, being more stable than

TABLE I

Complex	Thermal stability temp. °C	Decomposition temp. °C	Approx. residue formation temp. °C	Residue %	
				Theoretical	Observed
Ni(II)-HDCMBAOX	180	240	800	10.66	10.75
Cu(II)-HDCMBAOX	180	200	760	11.17	11.22
Pd(II)-HDCMBAOX	140	200	780	14.24	14.29

copper salicyldoxime⁵ which is stable upto 140°. It may be pointed out that the final weights of the residues were almost equal to weights of residues calculated from the molecular formulae of the complexes (Table I).

None of the Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) complexes with HDCMBAOX showed any change in colour with blue litmus or neutral FeCl₃. These show that there is no free phenolic group in the complex molecule.

Vosburgh and Copper's method⁶ showed that Ni(II) formed only one complex with HDCMBAOX having λ_{max} at 370 nm in the pH range 9.0-9.5. Subsequent studies were, therefore, undertaken at pH 9.2. Beer's law was valid upto 1010.5 ppm of Ni(II). There was no change in the absorbance within the experimental pH 9.0-9.5 of the system. There was again no change in colour even on keeping it for 25 hr and there was no change in the absorbance at room temperature either. The composition of the complex was found to be 1:2 (metal: ligand) by the application of Job's method⁷ of continuous variation and mole ratio method⁸. Ringbom method⁹ was applied for the determination of optimum concentration range for effective concentration determination of Ni(II) and it was found to be 33.69 to 78.62 ppm. The stability constant of the complex was calculated by the mole ratio method and was found to be 5.9833×10^6 . The standard free energy of formation was 9.707 kcal mol⁻¹ and entropy was 31.01 e.u. All these parameters were calculated at 40°.

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Influence of Concentration and Nature of Different Supporting Electrolytes on the Kinetics of Electrode Reaction of Bromophenol Blue

(Miss) NISHA JAIN and MUKHTAR SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Agra College, Agra-282 002

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WE have reported¹ the mechanism of polarographic reduction of bromophenol blue over the pH range 1.81-11.98 (BR buffer). The present paper describes the influence of concentration and nature of a number of supporting electrolytes, viz., NaNO₃, NaCl, NaClO₄, KNO₃, KCl, K₂SO₄, KCNS, Ba(NO₃)₂, Sr(NO₃)₂, Ca(NO₃)₂ and Mg(NO₃)₂, on the kinetics of the electrode reaction of bromophenol blue.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade and their stock solutions were prepared in conductivity water. Other experimental details are the same as mentioned earlier¹. The number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction process of bromophenol blue at d.m.e. was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon². This gave the value of n equal to 2 at pH 3.29 in the presence of different supporting electrolytes. Knowing the value of n, Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of the diffusion-coefficient, D, of bromophenol blue at different concentrations of supporting electrolytes. The potential-dependent rate constant, $k_{f,h}$, was calculated by Koutecky's^{3,4} method. The kinetic parameters, αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ were calculated⁵ from the plots of $\log k_{f,h}$ vs $E_{d.e.}$. Throughout the measurements, the current at the end of the drop (i.e. the maximum current) was recorded for the reasons given by Meites^{6,7}.

Results and Discussion

Bromophenol blue gives well-defined reduction wave at pH 3.29 (BR buffer) in the presence of different supporting electrolytes of varying concentrations (0.05-1.0 M). The wave-height in each case is diffusion-controlled as evidenced by the linearity of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$ plots and their passing through the origin. Various criteria^{8,9,10} of ascertaining the irreversibility of the electrode reaction of bromophenol blue indicate that the reduction process is